
Networks of Named Entities in Large Press Collections: Epistemological and Methodological Challenges

Martin Grandjean*¹

¹University of Lausanne, History Department – Switzerland

Abstract

Because of their massive, highly standardized nature, and more recently because of an intense digitization effort, press archives are sources of prime interest for digital history, a veritable "eldorado" to be explored (Bunout et al. 2023). Over the past decade, interest in these corpora has given rise to large-scale interdisciplinary projects, such as Numapresse(1), ViralTexts(2), NewsEye(3), Oceanic Exchanges(4), Living with Machines(5) or Impresso(6). This is particularly fertile ground for innovation, whether in the processing and enrichment of such data, its analysis by a whole range of distant reading tools, or its widespread availability to the general public via online interfaces (Ehrmann et al. 2023).

This contribution aims to discuss an emerging application of graph theory to these corpora: named entity co-occurrence networks. This approach consists of extracting names (named entity recognition, NER) from tens or hundreds of thousands of press articles to study the structure of common appearances of these terms. For example, names of people to establish an interpersonal network around a certain theme (Hicks et al. 2015), or places to understand the geographical space of a newspaper (Segal 2024). We support this reflection with an experiment based on several corpora of similar size, which show that the choice of keywords, newspapers and temporality have a varying influence on the type of networks produced (figure 1), and therefore their interpretation. The aim of this experiment is to provide a platform for addressing three key issues:

1. Epistemological challenge: How do we interpret these networks?

Co-occurrence networks in historical documents are an effective way of discovering the central protagonists of a corpus, but this is particularly true when they are the actual actors in the documents (e.g. senders and recipients, see Grandjean 2022). Therefore, does it make sense to assume that two people, institutions or places are connected if they appear in the same press article? The modeling assumes that a newspaper article is a well-defined unit, but it only really works if this physical unit in the newspaper is also a thematic unit, i.e. there is only one topic per article, which is often not the case. Also, how can we take into account the fact that the co-occurrence of two individuals in an article might be a sign of their antagonism, since the media often interview both sides when it comes to a political subject (Hicks et al. 2015, 578)? And given these questions about the meaning of such a co-occurrence, how can we "translate" the graph metrics (Grandjean and Jacomy 2019) so that they make sense in the "language" of the source? For example, is an individual with a high betweenness centrality really a "bridge" between others? Or does it rather mean

*Speaker

that he is a sufficiently "generalist" person to be quoted in articles involving people cited on different subjects?

2. Which corpus? The limits of keyword searches

Corpus composition is fundamental to press history (Oberbichler and Pfanzelter 2021). It is all the more important when it comes to conducting a large-scale quantitative analysis, as this only reinforces the biases involved. For example, working with named entities, and even more so if these are enriched with biographical databases, produces a bias in favor of elites, to the detriment of unnamed actors. Moreover, working with a corpus based on keywords consisting of one or more individuals' names presents significant challenges, as it can substantially distort the representation of these individuals within the named entity network. The creation of collections based on keywords is also problematic, since the material analyzed is conditioned around one or more notions selected a posteriori. What is the effect of the historian's retrospective judgment of a historical event on these corpora? And is the reverse, bottom-up approach, which consists in allowing the most frequent notions to appear in an unselected corpus (all articles published during a given period), viable for a network analysis in terms of the noise generated by this absence of keyword focus?

INSERT FIGURE 1 HERE

Figure 1. Examples of named entity (person) co-occurrence networks in press article corpora of the same size (between 9000 and 10000 articles) but produced based on keywords with very different scopes, enabling comparison between "thick" (several newspapers over a short period) or "extended" (a single newspaper over a longer period) corpora. Corpus produced on the Impresso interface on the basis of 5 Swiss newspapers (*La Liberté*, *L'Express*, *L'Impartial*, *Gazette de Lausanne* and *Journal de Genève*), then transformed into a graph with Table2Net (<https://medialab.github.io/table2net/>) and visualized with Gephi.

3. Can NER be effectively used for network analysis?

Specifically, what level of entity recognition accuracy do we need to make this solid? NER produces results that are just like our historical sources: imprecise due to imperfect OCR and badly disambiguated due to the many ways of naming the same people (Ehrmann et al. 2023). What percentage of error can we tolerate, and what effect does this have on the structure of the graph? Do inaccuracies result in a decrease in connectivity (one person with several names/titles recognized as several entities) or an increase (several people with similar names mistaken for one)? On the other hand, NER has the merit of bringing to light entities that are often overlooked, such as the names of people linked to the newspaper (editor-in-chief, journalists), reminding us that it's not the news itself that we're analyzing, but the content of an object that is far more complex. And a network visualization of these entities can show quite quickly which people have been recognized as several different entities (Mello 2023). One way of avoiding the problems associated with automatic NER might be to work with a controlled vocabulary of the names of the people we're looking for: this has the great advantage of scaling up a very qualitative approach to a very large scale very effectively, but it loses the benefits of the data-driven approach, which can reveal unexpected entities.

In conclusion, all these questions will lead us to examine the role of these network analyses in the research process. Are they exploratory tools, enabling the researcher to ask new questions and navigate the corpus, or can they really be used as analytical tools in their own right, whose quantified or visual results make it possible to describe the subject of the press articles?

Footnotes

(1) <http://www.numapresse.org>

(2) <https://viraltxts.org>

(3) <https://newseye.eu>

(4) <https://oceanicexchanges.org>

(5) <https://www.turing.ac.uk/research/research-projects/living-machines>

(6) <https://impresso-project.ch>

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"Impresso - Media Monitoring of the Past II. Beyond Borders: Connecting Historical Newspapers and Radio" ("Impresso") funded by the Swiss National Science Foundation (SNSF 213585) and the Luxembourg National Research Fund (17498891), <https://impresso-project.ch>.

Keywords: press history, historical network analysis, digital humanities, epistemology, critique